

MAPWORMS

Mimicking Adaptation
and Plasticity in
WORMS

D5.2 FIRST VERSION OF ACTUATION UNITS COMBINATION

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1 Introduction.....	4
2 Magnetic-responsive actuation units	6
2.1 Magnetic-responsive bending actuation unit	6
2.2 Magnetic-responsive twisting actuation unit	8
2.3 Combination of magnetic-responsive actuation units	10
2.3.1 Combination of bending actuation units to form a fluid-filled vesicle with extendable bellow proboscis	10
2.3.2 Combination of twisting actuation units to form a peristaltic pump.....	13
3 Temperature-responsive actuation units with variable stiffness	16
3.1 Temperature- and pH- responsive bending actuation units	16
3.2 Temperature- and light-responsive bending actuation units.....	18
3.3 Combination of temperature-responsive actuation units with variable stiffness	21
Conclusions	23
References	24

1 INTRODUCTION

The MAPWORMS project proposes a novel robot concept which aims at replicating the shape-morphing abilities of simplified forms of marine worms (Figure 1). Within this framework, Sipuncula, a class of unsegmented marine Annelida worms, serve as the primary source of bioinspiration for designing the final robots, thanks to their straightforward yet effective morphological structure (Figure 1A). This structure enables impressive deformations of their shape and protrusion abilities of part of their bodies. In the final robots, these abilities will be mimicked by combining synthetic soft actuation units into a smart and modular architecture capable of responding to various stimuli (Figure 1B).

Figure 1: (A) Body parts of Sipuncula worms which have been selected as main source of bioinspiration for the design of the final robots developed within the project. (B) Design concept of the worm-inspired robot that will be developed within the project. The final robots will feature a smart and modular architecture by combining actuation units capable of responding to different stimuli.

Specifically, the design goal of the project is to create a worm-inspired soft robot featuring various actuation units, each one capable of performing simple primitive movements (Figure 2). In each actuation unit, stiffness variations and internal stresses triggered by magnetic field, temperature, or pH variations, as well as light stimulation and chemical reactions, enable movement activation. These actuation units can be combined into more complex structures to achieve sophisticated motion and behaviors inspired by worms, and exploitable in different application scenarios. Like in the biological counterpart, the combination of these actuation units aims at activating fluidic transmission mechanisms, using active and passive structural elements to obtain different mechanical functionalities.

Depending on the actuation unit type (constitutive material, motion primitive and triggering mechanisms), different assembly strategies can be put in place to combine multiple units. These assembly techniques range from molding, use of inert assembly material (e.g. specific

glue and passive connection membranes), employment of self-healing hydrogels (e.g. exploiting the ability of hydrogels to autonomously repair damage to assemble multiple separated actuation units), etc.

Stimulus	Actuation units	Actuation units combination
Magnetic field	✓	✓
Temperature	✓	✓
Light		
pH		
Chemicals		

Figure 2: Different actuation units, capable of responding to specific stimuli, are being pursued and combined within the project. Markers in the two columns indicate the actuation units that have already been developed and combined in more complex architectures, respectively.

In this context, this Deliverable – “*First version of actuation units combination*” outlines the progress achieved during the initial 23 months of the project in combining actuation units based on smart materials capable of reacting to different stimuli, and described in the Deliverable – “*First working actuation unit*” which was submitted at the end of the 15th month of the project. Specifically, the report focuses on the combination of the following two types of actuation units, whose assembly has been evaluated as more promising:

- **Magnetic-responsive actuation units:** Magnetic soft composite materials were programmed by anisotropic magnetization of soft elastomers with embedded hard magnetic material particles to achieve desired mechanical functionalities. Through specific magnetization profiles, these actuation units can perform various primitive movements and achieve specific time-varying shapes by remote magnetic actuation.
- **Temperature-responsive actuation units with variable stiffness:** Thermo-responsive poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) (PNIPAAm) polymer was used for developing actuation units able to perform primitive movements in response to thermal stimuli. This polymer was combined with two innovative smart hydrogels capable of tuning their stiffness in response to pH variations and redox reactions, respectively. Redox reactions triggered by chemicals or light stimulation were employed to activate the redox-responsive actuation units.

These actuation units have already been combined into more intricate architectures. In the future, additional actuation units – currently under investigation – featuring responsiveness to different stimuli will be also combined and integrated into more complex architectures.

2 MAGNETIC-RESPONSIVE ACTUATION UNITS

Soft magnetic materials offer considerable potential for implementing programmable shape-morphing strategies. Indeed, complex mechanical functionalities that are unattainable by different approaches can be obtained through anisotropic magnetization programming of hard magnetic particles embedded into a soft matrix. Additionally, utilizing magnetic fields provides the advantage of remote operation, thus enabling contactless control.

A permanent magnet with a magnetic moment \mathbf{m}_1 produces a field $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{r})$ given by Equation 1, where \mathbf{r} is the displacement vector of the point at which the field is calculated, r is the magnitude of \mathbf{r} , and μ_0 is the vacuum permeability constant.

$$\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \left(\frac{3\mathbf{r}(\mathbf{m}_1 \cdot \mathbf{r})}{r^5} - \frac{\mathbf{m}_1}{r^3} \right) \quad (1)$$

A magnetic dipole with a magnetic moment \mathbf{m}_2 placed in a magnetic field \mathbf{B} will experience a force (\mathbf{F}) and Torque ($\boldsymbol{\tau}$) as given by equation 2 and 3, respectively:

$$\mathbf{F} = \nabla(\mathbf{m}_2 \cdot \mathbf{B}) \quad (2)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \mathbf{m}_2 \times \mathbf{B} \quad (3)$$

Utilizing this actuation strategy, two magnetic actuation units were developed: bending and twisting actuation units, individually discussed in the following subsections.

2.1 MAGNETIC-RESPONSIVE BENDING ACTUATION UNIT

Soft magnetic structures were developed to obtain bending primitive movements in response to an external magnetic stimulus. Specifically, the soft magnetic structures were manufactured using an active material made of Ecoflex 00-10 silicone (Shore 00-10; Smooth-On, Inc.) with embedded hard magnetic Neodymium Iron Boron (NdFeB) particles (MQFP-15-7, Magnequench GmbH), 5 μm in size, in a 1:1 mass ratio with the silicone. The actuation units feature a bilayer structure, consisting of a passive and an active rectangular layer (1.5 x 3 cm^2). The passive layer – made of Ecoflex 00-10 silicone without magnetic particles - allows for an easier combination of multiple units, acting as an inert assembly material.

For the fabrication of the bending actuation units, an Automatic Film Applicator Standard (model AB3652, TQC Sheen, Industrial Physics) was used to manufacture a 1mm-thick layer of the active material, ensuring the repeatability of the process. When the active layer was partially cured, the passive layer (thickness: 1 mm) was deposited over it. Subsequently, the two layers were left to cure fully, thus bonding together. Then, the desired rectangular shapes with sizes equal to 1.5 cm x 3 cm were cut from it through template routing.

When an external magnetic field is applied, the interaction between the magnetic moment m_2 of the actuation unit and the magnetic field B enables the bending movement of the actuation unit. To ensure the bending movement of the actuation units in response to a magnetic field, the actuation units were magnetized properly by using an Impulse Magnetizer (MAGNET-PHYSIK T-SERIES MF-AsA- \varnothing 25,0x60,0 mm-1218). Specifically, the actuation units were folded and placed in the Magnetizer such that the length of both folded parts of the actuation unit aligned with the Z-direction (Figure 3A). The magnetizer applied a strong magnetic field (1.9 T) along the +Z direction (Figure 3A), magnetizing all the magnetic particles in the +Z direction. As a result, when the actuation unit was unfolded, its two halves had opposite magnetization directions as shown in Figure 3B. Thanks to this magnetization profile of the actuation units, when an external magnetic field is applied along the Z direction, it produces a torque according to Equation 3 on each half of the actuation units, thereby aligning them along the Z axis. This results in the bending of the actuation units. By reversing the orientation of the external magnetic field from +Z to -Z, the opposite bending can be achieved as well (Figure 3B).

Figure 3: Magnetic bending actuation unit. (A) During the magnetization of the actuation units, a strong magnetic field is applied along the +Z direction which magnetizes the magnetic particles as shown in the figure. **(B)** After the magnetization, both halves of the actuation unit have an opposite magnetization in the resting configuration. Applying an external magnetic field along the +Z or -Z direction, the actuation unit bends.

The bending of the actuation units was characterized in terms of achievable bending angle (α in Figure 3B) under different intensity and direction of the external magnetic field. The results obtained for $\|B\| = 50$ mT (i.e., the highest magnetic field intensity applied during tests) are reported in Table 1, for both directions (+Z and -Z) of the external magnetic field.

Table 1 - Bending angles of the actuation units when 50 mT external magnetic field is applied along the +Z and -Z directions. Values reported in the table are the mean and standard deviation of 5 measurements on 5 samples.

Sample	+Z direction	-Z direction
Single active layer	$\alpha = 33.0^\circ \pm 1.3$	$\alpha = 17.3^\circ \pm 1.5$
Bi-layer structure	$\alpha = 47.2^\circ \pm 2.5$	$\alpha = 34.3^\circ \pm 2.5$

As expected, test results showed that bending of the actuation unit with the passive layer is lower than that observed with only the active layer. This is because the passive layer increases the bending area moment of the actuation unit while the magnetic torque acting on it remains the same. However, the passive layer is required to allow for a simple and effective combination of multiple actuation units. Additionally, when the external magnetic field is applied along the $-Z$ direction, the obtained bending angle is smaller than the bending angle reached in the opposite configuration. This means that the bending of the actuation unit is enhanced when the external magnetic field is applied along the $-Z$ direction. Indeed, as a single External Permanent Magnet (EPM) was used during tests, the generated magnetic field acting on the actuation unit was not uniform, since it is dependent on the distance between the EPM and the magnetic particles within the silicone of the actuation unit itself (Equation 1).

Figure 4A shows a relationship between magnetic field intensity and distance along the magnetization axis. Figure 4B and Figure 4C show a qualitative distribution of the magnetic fields generated by the EPM around the actuation unit. When the magnetic field is applied along $+Z$ direction, the strength of the magnetic field decreases at the extremities of the actuation unit, whereas when the magnetic field is applied along $-Z$ direction, the magnetic field intensity is higher at the extremities than at the centre point. As a result, the actuation unit experiences a greater torque when the magnetic field is applied along $-Z$ direction (Equation 3), thus performing higher bending (corresponding to a smaller α angle).

Additional details and considerations regarding these tests have been reported in the Deliverable D5.1 – “First working actuation unit”.

Figure 4: (A) Relationship between magnetic field intensity and distance along the magnetization axis. (B - C) Figure B and C show a qualitative distribution of the magnetic fields applied along $+Z$ and $-Z$ directions, respectively. The magnetic field is represented by arrows whose length represents the intensity of the magnetic field, and the direction represents the direction of the magnetic field.

2.2 MAGNETIC-RESPONSIVE TWISTING ACTUATION UNIT

Another type of magnetic actuation unit was developed to enable twisting primitives of movement. This kind of motion primitive is selected as particularly interesting due to its potential to enable peristaltic-type motion when multiple actuation units are assembled

(see details in section 2.3.2 Combination of twisting actuation units to form a peristaltic pump). Peristaltic-type motions can enable the development of robotic solutions that mimic the behaviour of worms and the fluidic transmission mechanisms regulating their movements.

As for bending magnetic actuation units, Ecoflex 00-10 silicone with embedded hard magnetic NdFeB particles (5 μ m in size, in a 1:1 mass ratio with silicone) was used. A 1mm thick film was obtained with the Automatic Film Applicator Standard. Then, eight rectangular strips (2 mm x 3 cm sizes) were cut using template routing.

As reported by Sitti et.al. [1], a peristaltic pump can be fabricated through the assembly of voxels which have been magnetized in specific directions. The resulting magnetic anisotropy of the peristaltic pump can also be achieved by combining eight twisting actuation units magnetized as shown in Figure 5A. Thus, a jig with an octagonal prism shape was used to achieve the desired magnetization profile that enables the twisting primitive movement. Specifically, each of the eight actuation units was given one full twist along its length and was fixed to one of the eight faces of the octagonal prism. All eight strips were magnetized together by applying a strong field (1.9 T) along a corner-to-corner diagonal of the octagon using a Vibrating Sample Magnetometer (VSM, EZ9, Microsense), as shown in Figure 5A. While each twisted strip was magnetized in the X direction (Figure 5B), it had a spiral magnetization profile when untwisted, an example of which is shown in Figure 5C. Thanks to this magnetization, each actuation unit can twist to form a spiral when an external magnetic field is applied in the direction perpendicular to its length.

Figure 5: (A) Magnetization of the eight actuation units to achieve a spiral magnetization profile using a jig. (B) The direction of magnetization at the top of the eight actuation units after the magnetization step. The spiral magnetization profile of each unit starts anticlockwise from this direction. (C) An example spiral magnetization profile achieved after untwisting the actuation units. The actuation unit is displayed with some transparency to show the arrows inside which represent the direction of magnetization along the body.

2.3 COMBINATION OF MAGNETIC-RESPONSIVE ACTUATION UNITS

2.3.1 COMBINATION OF BENDING ACTUATION UNITS TO FORM A FLUID-FILLED VESICLE WITH EXTENDABLE BELLOW PROBOSCIS

The bending actuation units were combined to actuate a soft water-filled vesicle, mimicking fluidic transmission mechanisms of worms based on the hydrostatic skeleton.

For actuating the vesicle, the bending units were magnetized following a similar approach as described in section 2.1. The bending units were folded in half lengthwise and positioned within the Magnetizer such that the two folded halves lay in the X-Y plane (Figure 6). Then, a strong magnetic field was applied in the +Z direction. As a result of this magnetization (Figure 6A), when the actuation unit is unfolded, its two halves have opposite magnetization directions as shown in Figure 6B: one half shows a magnetization profile along the +X direction, while the other half exhibits a magnetization profile along the -X direction. When the external magnetic field is applied in the +Z or -Z direction, a torque is generated according to Equation 3 on each half of the magnetic actuation unit, thereby aligning them with the direction of the magnetic field. This results in a bending of the actuation unit. Depending on the direction of magnetic field (-Z or +Z), the actuation units bend in two different configurations, as shown in Figure 6C.

Figure 6: (A) Configuration of the active layers during their magnetization. (B) Magnetization profile obtained after the magnetization: the two halves of individual active layers have opposite direction of magnetization, so that they can respond as shown in (C) depending on the direction of external magnetic field.

The design of the soft vesicle is shown in Figure 7. It was equipped with a soft bellow passive structure, acting as an extendable proboscis. The vesicle was made of Ecoflex 0010 silicone, in the shape of a square prism with rounded corners and 1mm-thick walls. On each of the four sides of the vesicle, one active magnetic layer was integrated, forming a bilayer structure with the 1mm-thick wall of the vesicle, like the bending actuation units described

above. 1 mm and 2 mm thick active layers were tested to analyse the required force for the vesicle deformation. However, 1mm-thick layers could not provide enough force and thus the 2 mm-thick ones were employed. The top surface of the vesicle had a hole on which the soft passive bellow proboscis was assembled (Figure 7, left). The bottom wall of the vesicle was reinforced with a 1mm-thick layer of Smooth-Sil 960 silicone (hardness: 60A), to limit the deformation of the vesicle base during actuation. In the final system, when the four actuation units bend under the application of an external magnetic field, the vesicle is squeezed, and water is forced into the bellow proboscis which elongates (Figure 7, right).

Figure 7: Water-filled soft vesicle actuated through bending magnetic actuation units: when the magnetic field is applied in the -Z direction, the actuation units bend, thus squeezing the vesicle and pushing the water into the bellow proboscis which elongates.

The body of the vesicle was fabricated using the moulding technique with Smooth-Sil 960 and Ecoflex 00-10 silicones (Figure 8A, B and C). Before moulding, the bending actuation units were placed into the mould such that they form the outermost layer of the vesicle. Thus, the Ecoflex 0010 silicone without magnetic particles was in contact with the actuation units during curing. This ensured that the active and passive materials stuck together, allowing for the assembly of the four actuation units.

Figure 8: Fabrication of the vesicle. (A) Placement of the active layers into the mold. (B) Casting of the base using Smoothsill 960 silicone. (C) Casting of the walls of the vesicle using Ecoflex 00-10 silicone.

The bellow proboscis was designed with its height equal to $h = 1.6$ cm, inner (d_i) and outer diameter (d_o) equal to $d_i = 0.7$ cm and $d_o = 1.4$ cm. The bellow proboscis itself was moulded separately from the vesicle using Ecoflex 00-10 silicone (Figure 9) and it was attached to the top of the vesicle using Sil-Poxy silicone glue (Smooth-On).

Figure 9: Soft passive bellow proboscis.

The vesicle actuation was preliminary tested using an EPM mounted on a robotic arm, such that the magnetization axis of the EPM aligned with the centreline of the vesicle. While moving the magnet along the Z-axis, the magnetic field at the base of the vesicle was increased up to 230 mT. As a result, the actuation units bent, thereby pushing the water into the bellow proboscis, and causing its elongation (Figure 10). In the future, the final design of the system will be further optimized to enhance the fluidic transmission mechanism and thus the final elongation capabilities of the bellow proboscis. Different designs of the proboscis

will also be investigated to obtain a proboscis contained within the main body in the resting state, which protrudes when the bending magnetic actuation units are activated.

Figure 10: (A) Magnetic actuation of the vesicle: schematic of the rest (off configuration) and actuated state (on configuration). (B) The vesicle in rest and (C) actuated states.

2.3.2 COMBINATION OF TWISTING ACTUATION UNITS TO FORM A PERISTALTIC PUMP

As anticipated in section 2.2 Magnetic-responsive twisting actuation unit, the combination of eight twisting magnetic actuation units has the potential to enable a peristaltic motion, mimicking the fluidic transmission mechanisms of worms. Indeed, each of the individual twisting actuation unit twists to form a spiral in the presence of an external magnetic field applied perpendicularly to its length. However, when eight of them are assembled as shown in Figure 11, the final combined motion is similar to a peristaltic wave if actuated through a rotating magnetic field in the X-Y plane. Thus, the final system has the potential to be used as a peristaltic pump.

Figure 11: (A-B) Top view of the magnetization of the eight strips before assembly. Then, four of the strips are rotated about the Z-axis by 180° to arrive at the final configuration shown in figure B. (C) The final assembled peristaltic pump has the actuation units in this final configuration with spacers between them. (D) When a magnetic field is applied in the direction shown by red arrows, the top section tries to align its magnetization with the applied field thereby becoming narrower. (E) When the magnetic field (represented by red arrows) is rotated anti-clockwise in the X-Y plane, the narrow section travels along the length of the peristaltic pump (represented in purple here).

For the pump manufacturing, the eight twisting actuation units were laid flat in a specific sequence depending on their magnetic configuration and held in place with 1mm space between them. Then, the 1 mm free spaces were filled with the passive elastomer (i.e., Ecoflex 00-10 silicone). Once cured, the ends of the final flat sheet were stuck together using an additional 1 mm spacer of passive elastomer, resulting in a cylinder with a 1.5 cm outer diameter and 3 cm height.

When a magnetic field perpendicular to the axis of the pump is applied, the hollow cylindrical shape of the assembled pump deforms, becoming narrower, as each strip tries to align its magnetization with the external magnetic field (Figure 11D). If the magnetic field then is rotated by an angle in the same direction as the rotation of the magnetic profile of the strips (Figure 5), the narrow section forms in correspondence of the layers whose magnetization is also rotated by the same angle. Therefore, by continually rotating the applied magnetic field, the narrow section travels along the length of the pump (Figure 11E). This results in generating a peristaltic motion in the pump, that allows for material transportation from one end to the other.

To demonstrate the capabilities of the pump, a 3D printed ball of 1 cm diameter was used for a preliminary test (see also the supplementary video [here](#)). The ball was placed at one end of the peristaltic pump which was fixed horizontally to prevent the ball from falling. The

EPM was also placed beside the pump such that when rotated, it would apply a rotating magnetic field along the entire length of the pump in a plane perpendicular to its axis (Figure 12). As the EPM was rotated, the ball travelled from one end to the other, thereby demonstrating the material transporting capabilities of the pump.

In the future, the aspect ratio and diameter of the peristaltic pump will be optimized to improve its efficiency in transporting fluids from one side to the other. Additionally, the reversibility of the transport, the static hydrostatic pressure, and the volumetric flow rate will be investigated.

Ball at distal end Ball in the middle Ball at proximal end

Figure 12: The actuation of the peristaltic pump under the influence of a rotating magnetic field whose direction of rotation is shown in red. The peristaltic motion is evident from the fact that a 3D printed ball placed at the distal end is pushed to the proximal end and out of the pump.

3 TEMPERATURE-RESPONSIVE ACTUATION UNITS WITH VARIABLE STIFFNESS

3.1 TEMPERATURE- AND PH- RESPONSIVE BENDING ACTUATION UNITS

The pH- and thermal-responsive actuation units feature a bilayer structure consisting of a DNA-based pH-responsive glucose oxidase (GOx)-loaded polyacrylamide (pAAm) layer combined with a thermo-responsive poly-N-isopropylacrylamide (pNIPAm) layer (not responsive to pH) (Figure 13). This bilayer structure allows for bending and variable stiffness actuation units.

Figure 13. Integration of pH- and temperature responsive hydrogels to produce bending variable stiffness actuation units.

The pH-responsive layer is made of DNA-based pAAm hydrogels or cryogels, loaded with GOx. In this solution, the bio-catalyzed aerobic oxidation of the metabolite (i.e., glucose) leads to local acidification in the hydrogel/ cryogel matrices. The main difference between cryogels and hydrogels is the preparation. Indeed, cryogels are prepared through analogue protocols to standard hydrogels synthesis but under freezing temperatures. During cryo-polymerization, crystalline solvent domains coated by concentrated crosslinked polymer matrices are formed. This frozen structure leads, upon thawing of the frozen matrix, to permanent structures with interconnected macropores and macrochannels, embedded in the crosslinked micropores of the polymeric backbone. Important structural and functional features arise from the interconnected macropores and the high-polymer content of the boundaries, as compared to analogue hydrogels matrices, composed of nano/micro solute containments and relatively homogenous polymeric-content distribution. Additional details can be found in the Deliverable - *Delivery of available smart responsive hydrogels for preliminary modelling and for devising integration possibilities*.

The design of pH-responsive DNA-based crosslinking units integrate a switch mechanism: while at neutral pH conditions, the nucleic acid strands form duplex structure crosslinking (high-stiffness), acidification leads to reconfiguration of the nucleic-acid crosslinking units

into an i-motif structure and a single-strand DNA, resulting in the decrease of crosslinking degree and of the stiffness (Figure 14A). The bio-catalytically stimulated pH-changes are reversible, thus, allowing for its application as biocatalytic pH-driven mechano-morphing material. Additionally, this solution presents a bio-inspired functionality where the biocatalytic consumption of a fuel metabolite (i.e., glucose) leads to mechanical actuations of the hydrogel/ cryogel.

Figure 14. (A) Schematic assembly of GOx-loaded pH-responsive DNA-based cryogel or hydrogel matrices, demonstrating metabolite-driven switchable stiffness properties. (B) Schematic formation of hybrid bilayer structures revealing reversible thermally actuated mechano-morphing properties. (C) Reversible thermally-induced mechano-morphing actuations of the

bilayer actuation unit. (D) Control over the bending degree by metabolite concentration (a-10mM, b-20 mM, and c-40 mM) and the time-intervals associated with the biocatalytic transformations.

A method to assemble comparable GOx-loaded, pH-responsive DNA-based cryogel and hydrogel matrices was investigated, demonstrating the beneficial response-times of the pH-regulated stiffness changes in the cryogel matrices (Figure 14A, Panel I) and reversible (Figure 14A, Panel II). The fast response time of the cryogels over the hydrogels originates from the pH-dictated reconfiguration of the cryogel matrices, that is due to the convectional flow instead of the diffusional one of the surrounding solution into and from the respective matrices. This work was published as a research paper entitled "Stiffness-Switchable, Biocatalytic pH-Responsive DNA-Functionalized Polyacrylamide Cryogels and their Mechanical Applications" in *Advanced Functional Materials Journal* [2].

The bending and variable stiffness actuation units consisting of a thermo-responsive pNIPAM cryogel layer and a DNA-based pH-responsive GOx-loaded pAAm layer (hydrogel or cryogel) revealed reversible thermally actuated mechano-morphing properties (Figure 14B), and cooperative metabolic (glucose oxidation) stimulated mechano-morphing functions. Specifically, the thermal-responsive mechano-morphing of the actuation units is fast and reversible (Figure 14C), and the cooperative bio-catalytically-driven mechano-morphing functions of the actuation units are controlled by the concentration of the metabolite, and by the time-interval of the biocatalytic transformations (Figure 14D).

3.2 TEMPERATURE- AND LIGHT-RESPONSIVE BENDING ACTUATION UNITS

The thermal and light-responsive, redox-driven actuation units feature a bilayer structure consisting of a redox-responsive $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}$ -CMC (CarboxyMethyl Cellulose) gel layer combined with a thermo-responsive pNIPAM layer (Figure 15). The $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}$ -CMC gel allows control over the stiffness properties by $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}$ redox reactions that are induced by chemical triggers or by light. Furthermore, Fe^{2+} is aerobically oxidized, leading to the autonomous restoration of Fe^{3+} -ions. Thus, through the design of high-stiffness gel crosslinked by Fe^{3+} -CMC, and their reduction by chemical means or by light, low-stiffness gel is formed due to lower crosslinking degree by Fe^{2+} -ions. Furthermore, aerobic oxidation of Fe^{2+} to Fe^{3+} restores the high-stiffness Fe^{3+} -CMC, allowing the development of gel matrices with transient dissipative stiffness changes. The chemical, and light-induced transient stiffness-changes of the gels were utilized for transient dissipative load-release and bending of the actuation units.

Figure 15. Integration of light-triggered redox-responsive and thermal-responsive gels to produce bending variable stiffness actuation units.

Specifically, the gel is composed of Fe^{3+} -crosslinked carboxymethyl cellulose (Fe^{3+} -CMC) and revealed redox-responsive stiffness-changes where the Fe^{3+} -CMC gel exhibits higher stiffness and Fe^{2+} -CMC showed lower stiffness. Chemical reducing agents or light-induced electron transfer reduction of Fe^{3+} -CMC to Fe^{2+} -CMC using Ru(II)-tris-(bipyridine) complex as photosensitizer results in the transition of Fe^{3+} -CMC to Fe^{2+} -CMC. The triggered transition of Fe^{3+} -CMC to Fe^{2+} -CMC is accompanied by the aerobic reoxidation of the Fe^{2+} -CMC to Fe^{3+} -CMC, leading to the autonomous transition from lower stiffness to higher stiffness (Figure 16A). That is:

leads to a dissipative gel material, revealing transient and temporal stiffness transitions (Figure 16B). By loading the gel with Texas Red-modified dextran, the temporal stiffness-changes of the gel are implemented for the transient and switchable release of load (Figure 16C). This study was accepted for publication as a research paper entitled "Chemical and Photochemical Driven Dissipative $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{Fe}^{2+}$ -Ion Crosslinked Carboxymethyl Cellulose Gels Operating Under Aerobic Conditions: Applications for Transient Controlled Release and Mechanical Actuation" in ACS Journal of American Chemical Society Journal.

Figure 16. (A) Schematic assembly of Fe^{3+} -crosslinked carboxymethyl cellulose gel revealing redox-derived stiffness-changes. (B) Temporal stiffness transitions of Fe^{3+} -CMC \rightarrow Fe^{2+} -CMC \rightarrow Fe^{3+} -CMC. (C) Transient and switchable release of load.

Furthermore, Bilayer pNIPAM/ Fe^{3+} / Fe^{2+} -CMC hybrid structures were developed for the operation of thermal/light-induced mechano-morphing bending actuation units (Figure 17A). The transient thermally induced and light-guided mechano-morphing activities of the actuation units were demonstrated (Figure 17B). The transient operations of the actuation units were dictated by the crosslinking degree of the gel by Fe^{3+} / Fe^{2+} and by the irradiation dose of the gel, stimulating the reductive photosensitized transformation of gel from Fe^{3+} -CMC to Fe^{2+} -CMC (Figure 17C). It should be noted that the autonomous reoxidation of Fe^{2+} -CMC leads to dissipative bending behavior, leading to the reversed actuation (i.e toward straightening of the device), and application of room temperature induces full recovery of the bent structure.

Figure 17. (A) Schematic assembly of bilayer actuation units for the operation of thermal/light-induced mechano-morphing bending. (B) Transient thermally induced and light-guided mechano-morphing bending and straightening. (C) Transient operations of the device with different irradiation time-intervals.

3.3 COMBINATION OF TEMPERATURE-RESPONSIVE ACTUATION UNITS WITH VARIABLE STIFFNESS

The bending variable stiffness actuation units previously introduced are based on bilayer structures that can be triggered by diverse auxiliary stimuli. Their combination has the potential to allow for the achievement of worm-inspired robots where signal-triggered actuation is activated by programmed auxiliary signals, enabling mechanically induced motility. Towards this goal, different bilayer actuation units with hybrid responsiveness can be combined into chain-like structures with enhanced complexity. The triggering of stiffness changes in the different bilayer actuation units allows for the development of temporal operating structures.

In this context, preliminary experiments to combine 2-unit-bilayer structures with orthogonal thermo-responsiveness were carried out (Figure 13). The integration of the actuation units is based on the construction of DNA-modified bilayer structures, exhibiting complementarity. Self-healing of the 2-hybrid layers leads to the integrated assembly. Bilayer constructs following this concept were synthesized to include pNIPAM thermo-responsive gels in

counter orientations. Upon heating/cooling the hybrid structures, counter-bending of the integrated actuation units resulted in temporal wave-like gel structures. This experiment suggests that self-healed actuation units yielding extended structures could be envisioned. By the programmed actuation of the different segments of the self-healed extended structure, programmed motility could be achieved.

Figure 18. Orthogonal thermo-responsive 2-unit-bilayer constructs actuations. In Figure A and B, the thickness of the actuation units was 1.6 mm and 3.2 mm, respectively. pH during these tests was constant. The different images show the bending movement of the actuation units activated by the temperature changes.

In the employed gel matrices, light responsiveness was obtained through an auxiliary photosensitizer. The integration of photosensitizer units into the gel matrix could lead to biomimetic light-responsive worm-inspired robots. In the future, the integration of semiconductor Quantum Dots (QDs) (i.e., nanoscale semiconductor particles with unique optical and electronic properties that arise due to quantum confinement effects) as photosensitizer elements driving the transient mechano-morphing of the actuation units is suggested as a pathway to follow this challenge. Moreover, the integration of different photosensitizers in different segments of polymeric hybrid bilayer constructs could be pursued. The addressable wavelength-controlled excitation of different actuation units could lead to mechano-morphed structures of enhanced complexity/functionality, and eventually, to light-stimulated motility of the final structures.

CONCLUSIONS

The MAPWORMS project introduces an innovative robot concept inspired by the shape-morphing abilities of marine worms, particularly Sipuncula. The project aims at developing worm-inspired soft robots capable of simple primitive movements through various actuation units, responsive to stimuli such as magnetic fields, temperature changes, pH variations, and chemical reactions. This document outlined the development of magnetic-responsive and temperature-responsive actuation units.

Magnetic-responsive bending and twisting actuation units have been designed and characterized under different magnetic field intensities and directions. These units demonstrate potential applications in achieving peristaltic-type motions and fluidic transmission mechanisms. The actuation was performed with an EPM which cannot produce uniform fields. However, the magnetic field strength values were assumed to be constant and equal to the values reported in this deliverable. In the future, an electromagnetic coil system would be used for actuation which is able to produce uniform magnetic fields and gradients.

Moreover, temperature-responsive actuation units with variable stiffness have been developed. These units consist of bilayer structures combining pH-responsive hydrogels with thermo-responsive polymers. The reversible stiffness changes in response to pH alterations or redox reactions enable diverse mechano-morphing functionalities, offering possibilities for controlled material transport and load release.

Further investigations will involve the optimization of the smart and modular architecture, combining the described actuation units, aiming at achieving worm-inspired robots with enhanced motility and functionality. Future developments will also include the combination of different actuation units into complex architectures.

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